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Executive summary

Within the framework of the NewLife4Drylands (NL4D) Project, the A3 action aims to structure a procedure for assessing soil degradation, monitoring this process and assessing the restoration actions that need to be carried out to counter this phenomenon at local level. More specifically, this contribution (deliverable D.3.1) sets out an analysis that attempts to examine the correlations between the satellite indices and indicators (set out in action A2) and the information generated by the soil that has been collected for every one of the pilot sites involved in the project.

The structure of the research on the correlations is considered a necessary and essential step for the A3 action and aims to identify any potential and optimal possibilities and useful information for achieving the action's aim. It examines a process that uses satellite-generated indices/indicators and monitors the effectiveness of the restoration actions required for fighting soil degradation at local level.

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1. Introduction

The NewLife4Drylands (NL4D) Project aims to create a model that supports decisions, enabling the user to identify sustainable solutions (Nature Based Solutions - NBS) and monitor their efficiency in Mediterranean areas undergoing soil degradation, and in particular those undergoing desertification, and it does so using Remote Sensing indices.

The UNCCD definition refers to land degradation (LD) as the “reduction or loss of biological or economic productivity and complexity of rainfed cropland, irrigated cropland, or range, pasture, forest and woodlands resulting from land uses or from a process or combination of processes, including processes arising from human activities and habitation patterns” (Those, 1994).

The Model is based on an operational procedure that aims to support the identification of soil degradation factors, solutions for the restoration thereof and indices for the medium and long-term monitoring of the sites’ conditions and the efficiency of the said solutions.

The recent availability of open free high-spatial, temporal and spectral-resolution satellite data (taken, for example, from the EU Copernicus programme) is a significant opportunity for also obtaining measurements for sites that are too difficult to reach, or for which there are no available surveys or official and updated maps. Remote sensing is considered the main tool for implementing medium and long-term monitoring, since it allows the insufficient information obtained on site to be supplemented with reliable, homogeneous, and rapid results that are sometimes obtained at zero cost or at a very reduced cost when compared to traditional monitoring.

With a view to achieving the maximum consistency of the identified solutions for all of the project’s study areas, not only has the possibility of obtaining indices that are useful for monitoring the various phenomena of degradation been assessed, but also the possible availability of free sources of satellite images has been looked at.

The Action A2 outcomes (see Deliverable A2.1) have identified a series of remote sensing-processed indices and indicators. Scientific and technical procedures have been developed with

a view to extracting such indices and indicators from open satellite data at local level and doing so for each study site involved in the project. The said indices and indicators have been selected on the basis of scientific and technical literature, of the consortium members' experience and the debates with the Advisory Board.

Action A3 is responsible for defining the monitoring model, which is the tool that connects the degradation phenomena, the Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and the remote sensing monitoring indicators, providing assistance in the decision-making process for the purpose of the adaptive management of degraded soil restoration actions, improving the provision of ecosystem services.

The deliverable D3.1 is devoted to the methodology for statistical analysis description on the base of the specific list of indicators from A2. The outputs of statistical analysis will be released in the final deliverable for action A3.

An analysis is carried out on the correlations between the indices identified for the purpose of monitoring the degradation processes and the available in-situ data collected from monitoring activities conducted in cases studied throughout the project. The analysis aims to identify the most promising remote-sensed indices that concern the examined areas' degradation and specific pressures.

This document is structured in five essential parts: The first part is dedicated to the importance of the environmental monitoring of soil degradation processes and more specifically the potential of remote sensing, which is an effective means of structuring monitoring methodologies and intervention protocols for the purpose of countering such phenomenon. The second part deals with the exploration of the data obtained from the project (remote sensing indices and indicators) and the data obtained from ground samples collected in the previous LIFE Projects that have been made available for the purpose of NL4D's objectives. The third part is dedicated to a scientific review of the use of satellite monitoring for the purpose of analyzing the restoration interventions' efficiency, particularly with regard to the correlations between data collected in the field and data generated from remote sensing, focusing its attention mostly on the statistic methodologies used for that purpose. The fourth part describes the statistical methodology identified for the purpose of analyzing the correlations to

for the pilot sites taking part in the project, whereas the last part is dedicated to a first description of the design of the Monitoring Model and in particular the Decision Map's structure behind.

2. Degradation monitoring

Soil degradation has become one of the most critical environmental and socio-economic problems in the world (UNCCD, 2017). It is estimated that around 25% of the world's land surface is highly degraded, whereas 36% is moderately degraded (UNCCD, 2013). Other studies claim that the world's land surface affected by soil degradation should rise to 90% within 2050 (Pereira and Bogunovic, 2018). Soil degradation is defined as the tenacious reduction of biological and economical productivity, which prevents the ability of soil to provide ecosystem services (Lead et al., 2005).

The NL4D Project aims to counter soil degradation that leads to desertification. It involves pilot sites located in Mediterranean areas that are already characterized by scarce water resources and that show already ongoing processes of desertification caused by fires, erosion and soil salinization, diffusion of invasive species and strong pressure from herbivore fauna.

The implementation of Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN) must deal with huge challenges in achieving the global sustainable development goals indicated in the 2030 Agenda, making the monitoring of soil degradation and the definition of the determining factors of vital importance (Jiang et al., 2022).

At the moment, soil degradation monitoring is based on the opinion of experts in the field, on the application of biophysical models, and on measurements collected in the field and satellite observation (Gibbs and Salmon, 2015). A direct approach consisting of in-the-field evaluations of soil degradation, which consist of local sampling techniques (Beckedahl and De Villiers, 2000), are undoubtedly a valid way of gaining objective detailed information on soil degradation occurring at a local level. However, this approach is often criticized for being expensive in terms of time, labor, cost and is mostly applicable only on small surfaces (Niemic, 2009).

On the other hand, an approach based on remote sensing, which includes the use of evenly and regularly collected satellite data on a vast geographic area (Gibbs and Salmon, 2015) provides a plausible and coherent alternative that is useful for monitoring soil degradation on a multitemporal and operative level. Relevant experiments on remote sensed data often use spectral vegetation indices to map soil degradation (Nzuza et al., 2021).

NL4D's main aim is to monitor, through the use of remote sensing techniques, the application, scalability and replication of Nature Based Solutions (NBS) used for restoring degraded areas; the said techniques allow:

- the features of arid areas to be identified;
- the sustainable solutions that could be successfully implemented in degraded arid areas (i.e. improving vegetation cover and productivity in areas that are vulnerable to ongoing desertification) to also be identified;
- the medium and long-term action that could be taken in connection with the desertification of land to be monitored, so as to better evaluate the efficiency of the restoration and improve the sustainable management of soil.

Despite the numerous studies published in scientific magazines demonstrating the efficiency of satellite data as a valid device for monitoring soil degradation (for example in the case of remote sensing applied to the monitoring of soil salinity at a local level), there are still problems in resolving the imbalance between the measurements collected from the ground and the satellite data, since multispectral bands are not sufficiently accurate in detecting in a precise manner the subtle physiological differences caused by saline stress (use of remote sensing to evaluate the effects of environmental factors on soil salinity in semi-arid areas). The same problem affects other types of satellite-generated indices, such as, for example those concerning vegetation that are widely used in the study of land surface phenology for the purpose of tracing its response to climatic variables.

Some studies, which have researched the relationships between different vegetation indices calculated by using ground measurement-based remote sensing and phenology technologies, demonstrate the efficiency of phenology-related data calculated with the help of remote sensing and suggest that they should be used for the soil cover in regions with more complex interactions between climatic variables and phenology (Zhou et al., 2022).

The changes in the land-management systems are for the most part a result of human decision-making processes at various levels, from the local land management to national soil-use plans and global trade agreements. An improved understanding of the status, trends and the

consequences of changes in land are relevant for the purpose of involving Land System Science (LSS) in sustainability transformations (Dong et al., 2019).

The recognition of one or more factors of soil degradation, the mapping and the monitoring of these processes on land lead, in light of the foregoing, to the need to develop public policies for managing land in a sustainable manner other than the identification of priority areas in which land must be recovered. The need to collect all of the information coming from the measurements taken in-situ and the information obtained from the most innovative satellite processes is increasing and gives rise to an overview of decision-making processes that allows governance to be guided towards the goal of monitoring and restoring extremely degraded areas.

Numerous studies that focus on monitoring soil degradation through remote sensing indices are testing a decision tree-based model for the purpose of detecting degraded areas and demonstrating that, by correctly supplementing satellite indices generated from in-situ measurements and allowing the severity of the soil degradation to be assessed (as well as combining other indices), the algorithm is capable of providing precise, detailed and accurate analyses of the process (Marcia et al., 2021).

The results of these studies provide valid suggestions for protocols that could provide public authorities with assistance in adopting sustainable policies and recovering degraded areas.

The main goal, within the framework of NL4D's technical A3 action, is to identify the existing correlations between the remote sensing indices and the information obtained from ground samples using, when and where this is possible, information and datasets found in studies conducted in other LIFE Projects that have dealt with the same pilot sites. This analysis presupposes the will to explore the following essential aspects:

- the intrinsic correlation between indices generated by satellite data and data from ground samples so as to improve the gap and possible inconsistencies between two measurements;
- the setting of the satellite index at a pre-defined level/degree of degradation with the help of in-the-field measurements;
- the extrapolation of useful information that refers to the other variables that could mostly give rise to a specific type of degradation.

3. Remote Sensing Indices and Indicators

In pursuing the objective of building an identification methodology that analyzes the correlations between indices derived from satellite images and information collected from the ground, it has become necessary to retrace the list of potential remote sensing indices and indicators defined for the purpose of specifically monitoring each degradation process, starting from the list of indices and indicators defined in action A2 shown in

Table 1.

The essential variables (EV), which are a key group of measurements required for monitoring the said goals, can be obtained, in the form of simple indices and indicators derived from the indices, through remote sensing data used as a proxy to evaluate the quantification and the mapping of soil degradation. The relevant effort of the NewLife4Drylands project consists in extracting those indices and indicators at local level, as is the case with the study sites, and trying to satisfy the requests made by local institutional decision-makers for details that are difficult to reach with global/pan European (EU) level services (i.e. Copernicus), as well as for details on ground monitoring that are not available.

More specifically, a series of well-known indices and indicators generated from remote sensing data that have been widely tested in the reference scientific bibliography have been selected. The technical procedure for their extraction at local level from open satellite data has been indicated for each study site (

Table 1).

The said indices/indicators have been selected on the basis of scientific and technical literature and the expertise of the project's partner members, as well as on the basis of discussions had with the advisory board. There is a need to provide indications that are useful for identifying/monitoring the different types of soil degradation to which the pilot sites identified in the project have been subjected.

With a view to conducting research on the identification of the soil degradation process, a spatial range and timeframe that sets out the scale thereof and how open satellite sources are

to be searched for must be defined. This definition is also the possible basis for analyzing the correlations between the ground data and the value of the indices.

Table 1. Indices and Indicators

INDICES		
Type	Acronym	Description
Vegetation Indices	NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
	GNDVI	Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
	MSAVI ₂	Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index
	OSAVI	Optimized Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index
	NDRE	Normalized Difference RedEdge
	ARVI	Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index
	EVI ₂	Enhanced Vegetation Index 2
	REP	RedEdge Position
	NBR	Normalized Burn Ratio
	NBR ₂	Normalized Burn Ratio 2
Water Indices	NDWI ₁	Normalized Difference Water Index 1
	NDWI ₂	Normalized Difference Water Index 2
	MNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index
Soil Indices	NDSI	Normalized Difference Soil Index
	NDBSI	Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index
	BI	Bare Index
Soil Salinity Indices	SSI ₁	Soil Salinity Index-1
	SSI ₂	Soil Salinity Index-2
	SSI ₃	Soil Salinity Index-3
	SI	Salinity Index
	SASI	Soil Adjusted Salinity Index
Drought/Dryness Indices	NDDI	Normalized Difference Drought Index
	DSI	Desertification Soil Index
INDICATORS		
SDG 15.3.1 (V2 released on March, 29th 2021)	"proportion of land that is degraded over total land area"	Land Cover (LC) change (Trend in LC)
		Land Productivity loss
		Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) decline
		Loss of habitat quality
		Burnt Areas

		<i>Fragmentation Index</i>
		<i>Areas of potential impact</i>
		<i>Density of artificial LC</i>
		<i>Increasing unsealed areas</i>
SDG 11.3.1	"ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate"	<i>Land Consumption Rate</i>
		<i>Population Growth Rate</i>
ESA(I)	Environmentally Sensitive Areas to Desertification (Index)	<i>Soil Quality Index (SQI)</i>
		<i>Climate Quality Index (CQI)</i>
		<i>Vegetation Quality Index (VQI)</i>
		<i>Management Quality Index (MQI)</i>

Insights about specific technical information regarding the methods for calculating the indices and the metadata correlated to the aforementioned indicators has made it possible to obtain useful information about the structural organization of the correlations' analysis. Predicting and analyzing the structure of the outputs obtained as a result of processing satellite images has led to excluding from datasets some of the information used for analyzing the correlations, as well as all the indicators generated from the 11.3.1 e 15.3.1 SDG and the ESA Environmentally Sensitive Areas to Desertification (Index) indicator. This exclusion is justified by the need to consider quantitative or binary variables (e.g. presence/absence) within the statistical analysis of the correlations.

All of the indices calculated for the different project sites are, on the other hand, taken into consideration for the purpose of the statistical analysis.

4. Ground data available for pilot sites

With a view to facilitating the collection and cataloguing of the datasets for each pilot site, the partners responsible for each such site were asked to complete a list (that was specific for each case study), in which they reported the effective availability of the requested data, according to examples of previously defined types of data. Table 2 sets out the type of data for which a specific request was made for the purpose of verifying the availability thereof.

Table 2. Data type field

Area limits/boundaries (shape file with perimeters, polygon); Area/subarea size (ha/km ²)
Digital Elevation Model (DEM), Aspect, Slope
Surface hydrology
Soil Organic Carbon, Soil Texture, Soil depth, Bulk density, Soil E.C., Soil pH
Land surface temperature
Hydrological characteristics of the soil (e.g. infiltration)
Land Net Primary Productivity (gC/m ² /day)
Biodiversity Index
Weeds cover (%)
Invasive species cover (%)
Water table
Land use/land cover
Geology/Lithology
Soil map
Soil erosion map (Mg/ha/yr)
Landscape elements (hedges, stone walls, rushes, open ditches, springs, solitary trees, etc.)
Green infrastructures
Areas affected by wildfires
Forest structure
Climate time-series
Vegetation and habitat map
Lithology
Evaporation
Landslide danger
Renewable energy infrastructures
Faults/cracks
Topographic map

Phenology map

Various other information concerning each type of data that has been considered available has been requested, such as, for example, the (vector, raster, etc.) format of such data, the year of reference and the spatial range considered. In the case of data taken from samples collected from a number of points, such as measurements taken from the ground, a request was made to specify the number of points, the sample density and the sampling method.

The first step was to verify, for each site, the data availability and verify the consistency of the information reported in the lists of data made available in the dataset of each site.

5. Study areas

The six study sites have a wide variety of Mediterranean ecosystems, namely arid, mountainous, and coastal areas, with high or lower elevations and are threatened by different pressures that lead to soil degradation (see deliverable A1.1). Therefore, the analysis of data from remote sensing is not site-dependent, but specific for the Mediterranean ecosystems, and identifies a suitable protocol for monitoring their state of degradation. The remote sensing indicators can offer indications for evaluating the efficiency of the NBS solutions for the purpose of recovering the degraded areas in the manner implemented in the study sites.

Set out below is a summary for each of the study cases that describes the specific features of each site, the main threats to which it is subjected and the type of degradation affecting it. A list of indicators that can potentially monitor the evolution thereof is indicated for each type of degradation that has been detected. Finally, the available data that has been collected and the potential use thereof for the purpose of conducting a correlation analysis between satellite indices and ground samples has been recorded.

Palo Laziale

Figure 1. Palo Laziale

The Palo Laziale forest (Figure 1), which is located on a seafront 40 km away from Rome, is one of the last remaining examples of an ancient floodplain forest that in the past stretched over the entire coastline of central-western Italy. It forms the core of the 'Bosco di Palo Laziale', Natura 2000 site located in Italy (SCI IT6030022) covering about 50 ha and is predominantly composed of the

'Pannonian-Balkan turkey oak-sessile oak-forest' (91M0) type of habitat, as well as transient-freshwater types of habitat that are rich in biodiversity, such as the 'Mediterranean temporary ponds' (*3170).

The Palo Laziale habitats and wildlife (e.g. Hermann's tortoise, European pond turtle, etc.) face several threats, including climate change, inappropriate forest and water management and shrub encroachment. In particular, an increasing exposition to soil aridity and extreme drought events have led to a dramatic case of forest dieback in Palo Laziale. The first signs of forest degradation were observed in 1995, and continued without interruption until 2003. A tremendous summer heatwave caused the death of about 40% of the adult trees in that year. Subsequently, a concurrent pathogenic attack of the "fungus *B. mediterranea*" did the rest. Therefore, about 80% of the initial forest canopy was lost in 2015. The site owners appointed ecologists from the Sapienza University of Rome to identify the primary causes of the forest dieback. A set of restoration ecology solutions were conceived from that multidisciplinary study and started to be implemented when the LIFE PRIMED project was approved.

Set out below is the matrix (Table 3) that deals with types of degradation identified for the Palo Laziale site and the satellite indices that potentially allow it to be identified and monitored.

Table 3. Palo Laziale Indices and degradation processes

INDICES			DEGRADATION PROCESSES			
Type	Acronym	Description	Aridification	Decline in vegetation community functioning	Decline in vegetation cover/biomass	Habitat loss
Vegetation Indices	NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index		X	X	X
	GNDVI	Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index		X	X	X
	MSAVI ₂	Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index		X	X	X
	OSAVI	Optimized Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index		X	X	X
	NDRE	Normalized Difference RedEdge		X	X	X
	ARVI	Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index		X	X	X
	EVI ₂	Enhanced Vegetation Index 2		X	X	X
	REP	RedEdge Position		X	X	X
	NBR	Normalized Burn Ratio				
	NBR ₂	Normalized Burn Ratio 2				
Water Indices	NDWI ₁	Normalized Difference Water Index 1			X	
	NDWI ₂	Normalized Difference Water Index 2				
	MNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index				
Soil Indices	NDSI	Normalized Difference Soil Index	X			X
	NDBSI	Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index	X			X
	BI	Bare Index	X			X
Soil Salinity Indices	SSI ₁	Soil Salinity Index-1	X			
	SSI ₂	Soil Salinity Index-2	X			
	SSI ₃	Soil Salinity Index-3	X			
	SI	Salinity Index	X			
	SASI	Soil Adjusted Salinity Index	X			X
Drought/Dryness Indices	NDDI	Normalized Difference Drought Index	X			X
	DSI	Desertification Soil Index	X			X

Tifaracas

Figure 2. Tifaracas

Tifaracas (Figure 2) is a desertified area located in the municipality of Artenara, on the island of Gran Canaria. It is located within the El Nublo Rural Park, which in turn forms part of the Gran Canaria Biosphere Reserve. The area is classified as a Site of Community Interest (SCI) and Special Area of Conservation (SAC) that is included in the

Natura 2000 Network. Although the area has a high risk of desertification, we find vegetation typical of the island's arid and semi-arid environments, with a predominance of herbaceous species, even though they have a very low cover. Within the framework of the LIFE Green Link project (LIFE15 CCA / SE / 125), some 4000 seedlings of native forest species, trees and shrubs have been planted with the "Cocoon" system. The aim of planting them is to reverse the desertification process and improve the ecological connectivity of the adjacent Canary Island pine forests.

The area is severely affected by desertification processes, which are aggravated by reduced rainfall, recurrent forest fires and herbivores, and in particular the abundant presence of feral goats. Average annual rainfall is below 200 mm, even though it has not exceeded 100 mm in recent years, in which dry periods without rain have lasted more than 10 months, making it very difficult to reforest the area in an attempt to establish vegetation cover that protects the soil from erosion. Even though the high stoniness of the soil means that it is not particularly vulnerable to erosion, the low vegetation cover, the steep slope of the hillsides and the torrential rains favor erosion processes. These processes have led to the loss of fertile soil, making it even more difficult to establish vegetation cover.

Set out below is the matrix that describes the types of degradation identified in the Palo Laziale site and the satellite indices that potentially allow it to be identified and monitored.

Table 4. Indices and degradation processes for Tifaracas.

INDICES			DEGRADATION PROCESSES							
Type	Acronym	Description	Aridification	Forest fires	Over-grazing	Soil organic matter decline	Soil erosion by water and wind	Decline in vegetation community functioning	Decline in vegetation cover/biomass	Habitat loss
Vegetation Indices	NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index		X	X			X	X	X
	GNDVI	Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index		X	X			X	X	X
	MSAVI ₂	Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index		X	X			X	X	X
	OSAVI	Optimized Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index		X	X			X	X	X
	NDRE	Normalized Difference RedEdge		X	X			X	X	X
	ARVI	Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index			X			X	X	X
	EVI ₂	Enhanced Vegetation Index 2			X			X	X	X
	REP	RedEdge Position			X			X	X	X
	NBR	Normalized Burn Ratio		X						
	NBR ₂	Normalized Burn Ratio 2		X						
Water Indices	NDWI ₁	Normalized Difference Water Index 1							X	
	NDWI ₂	Normalized Difference Water Index 2								
	MNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index								
Soil Indices	NDSI	Normalized Difference Soil Index	X		X	X				X
	NDBSI	Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index	X		X	X				X
	BI	Bare Index	X		X	X				X
Soil Salinity Indices	SSI ₁	Soil Salinity Index-1	X							
	SSI ₂	Soil Salinity Index-2	X							
	SSI ₃	Soil Salinity Index-3	X							
	SI	Salinity Index	X							
	SASI	Soil Adjusted Salinity Index	X							X
Drought/Dryness Indices	NDDI	Normalized Difference Drought Index	X		X	X				X
	DSI	Desertification Soil Index	X		X	X				X

El Bruc

Figure 3. El Bruc

The counties of Anoia and Bages experienced a serious fire in July 2015, which burned 1,235 ha of forest located in the municipalities of El Bruc (Figure 3), Òdena, Castellfollit del Boix, Sant Salvador de Guardiola and Castellolí. A large part of the burnt forest was Aleppo pine (*Pinus halepensis*), which had already been burnt by a fire in 1986. The pines – which do not have a resprouting strategy but germinate –

are undergoing modest and variable regeneration throughout the area, possibly due to the intense drought that affected the area, especially in the years immediately after the fire. In the framework of the LIFE Green Link project (LIFE15 CCA / SE / 125), more than 20 ha of forest and agricultural species have been planted to recover the most degraded areas and favor the recovery of the agro-silvopastoral mosaic, which helps to reduce the area's vulnerability to future forest fires.

The area affected by the fire is located in the central area of Catalonia, which is characterized by a dry sub-humid climate, with an average rainfall of between 600 and 700 mm per year. It is located at an altitude of between 450 and 500 m above sea level. There is an average of less than 50 days of rain per year, with frequent periods of drought and water stress for plants, which have increased in recent years. Due to this factor, as well as the high recurrence of forest fires, these are areas with low natural regeneration that are affected by concentrated and diffuse erosion processes. Furthermore, like many areas in the Mediterranean, (and in particular areas in the Iberian Peninsula), this area has been affected by rural abandonment since the beginning of the 19th century, which has led to an expansion of the forest (mainly of white pine), which increases the risk of large forest fires. Therefore, there is an interest in promoting environmental restoration projects that favor the restoration of cultivated fields, as

well as the forest management of woodlands. Thinning the white pine forest during reforestation not only helps regenerate it after fires or other disturbances, but also helps the forest to have a good structure and good dynamics.

Set out below is the matrix (Table 5) of the types of degradation identified for the El Bruc site and the satellite indices that potentially allow such degradation to be identified and monitored.

Table 5. Indices and degradation processes for El Bruc

INDICES			DEGRADATION PROCESSES										
Type	Acronym	Description	Landscape modification	Aridification	Forest fires	Overshading	Soil organic matter decline	Soil erosion by water and wind	Decline in vegetation community functioning	Decline in vegetation cover/biomass	Habitat loss	Increase in invasive species	Trees encroachment
Vegetation Indices	NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	X		X	X			X	X	X	X	X
	GNDVI	Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	X		X	X			X	X	X	X	X
	MSAVI ₂	Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	X		X	X			X	X	X	X	X
	OSAVI	Optimized Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	X		X	X			X	X	X	X	X
	NDRE	Normalized Difference RedEdge	X		X	X			X	X	X		
	ARVI	Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index	X			X			X	X	X		X
	EVI ₂	Enhanced Vegetation Index 2	X			X			X	X	X		X
	REP	RedEdge Position	X			X			X	X	X		
	NBR	Normalized Burn Ratio			X								
	NBR ₂	Normalized Burn Ratio 2			X								
Water Indices	NDWI ₁	Normalized Difference Water Index 1	X							X			
	NDWI ₂	Normalized Difference Water Index 2	X										
	MNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index	X										

Soil Indices	NDSI	Normalized Difference Soil Index	X	X		X	X				X		
	NDBSI	Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index	X	X		X	X				X		
	BI	Bare Index	X	X		X	X				X		
Soil Salinity Indices	SSI ₁	Soil Salinity Index-1	X	X									
	SSI ₂	Soil Salinity Index-2	X	X									
	SSI ₃	Soil Salinity Index-3	X	X									
	SI	Salinity Index	X	X									
	SASI	Soil Adjusted Salinity Index	X	X							X		
Drought/Dryness Indices	NDDI	Normalized Difference Drought Index	X	X		X	X				X		
	DSI	Desertification Soil Index	X	X		X	X				X		

Alta Murgia

Figure 4. Alta Murgia

The SCI and SPA Murgia Alta Natura 2000 site (IT9120007) located in Southern Italy, has had a National Park since 2004. It is characterized by a millennial history of land use and is a typical Mediterranean agro-pastoral landscape (Figure 4) mainly occupied by semi-natural rocky dry grasslands that are traditionally used as

extensive pastures. The Alta Murgia semi-natural grassland ecosystem hosts numerous endemic, rare or trans-Adriatic distribution species. This area is considered of crucial importance for the conservation of wildlife and priority species.

During the last three decades, the dominant Alta Murgia semi-natural grassland ecosystem, which is characterized by endemic and threatened species, has been exposed, within and next to its borders, to accelerated processes of habitat degradation, fragmentation and biotic contamination of local biodiversity (i.e., woody encroachment) due to both agricultural intensification (transformation of grassland pastures as a result of agricultural cereal crop

intensification) and land abandonment. Furthermore, long-term below-average rainfall (climate change), an increase in either legal and illegal mining activities or wind farm infrastructures, fire events and the spread of invasive species have contributed to threaten the ecosystem, which is in danger of being destroyed.

Set out below is the matrix (Table 6) that describes the types of degradation identified for the Alta Murgia site and the satellite indices that potentially allow such degradation to be identified and monitored.

Table 6. Indices and degradation processes for Murgia Alta.

INDICES			DEGRADATION PROCESSES								
Type	Acronym	Description	Landscape modification	Aridification	Forest fires	Soil erosion by water and wind	Decline in vegetation community functioning	Decline in vegetation cover/bio mass	Habitat loss	Increase in invasive species	Trees encroachment
Vegetation Indices	NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	X		X		X	X	X	X	X
	GNDVI	Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	X		X		X	X	X	X	X
	MSAVI ₂	Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	X		X		X	X	X	X	X
	OSAVI	Optimized Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	X		X		X	X	X	X	X
	NDRE	Normalized Difference RedEdge	X		X		X	X	X		
	ARVI	Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index	X				X	X	X		X
	EVI ₂	Enhanced Vegetation Index 2	X				X	X	X		X
	REP	RedEdge Position	X				X	X	X		
	NBR	Normalized Burn Ratio			X						
	NBR ₂	Normalized Burn Ratio 2			X						
Water Indices	NDWI ₁	Normalized Difference Water Index 1	X					X			
	NDWI ₂	Normalized Difference Water Index 2	X								
	MNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index	X								

Soil Indices	NDSI	Normalized Difference Soil Index	X	X					X		
	NDBSI	Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index	X	X					X		
	BI	Bare Index	X	X					X		
Soil Salinity Indices	SSI ₁	Soil Salinity Index-1	X	X							
	SSI ₂	Soil Salinity Index-2	X	X							
	SSI ₃	Soil Salinity Index-3	X	X							
	SI	Salinity Index	X	X							
	SASI	Soil Adjusted Salinity Index	X	X					X		
Drought/Dryness Indices	NDDI	Normalized Difference Drought Index	X	X					X		
	DSI	Desertification Soil Index	X	X					X		

Nestos

Figure 5. Nestos

The Nestos River (Figure 5) forms the natural boundary between the Regions of Macedonia and Thrace, in north-eastern Greece. The Nestos Delta, created by the alluvial deposits of the river that have extended the land to the sea, covers an area of 55,000 ha. On account of its size and the variety of its habitats, the Delta is considered among

the most important wetlands of Greece and Europe. A significant feature of SCI GR1150010 is the riparian forest, which is a priority habitat according to EU Directive 92/43 and is one of the largest of its type in Mediterranean.

The Nestos River is used by both countries (Bulgaria and Greece) for municipal water supply, irrigation and hydroelectric power production. The past estimated mean runoff of the River was 20 to 30 m³/s and an annual discharge 1,120 mio. m³. The River is the most important water resource in its region and has been the subject of bilateral negotiations for many years. The famous delta is a National Park, but it is, on account of pollution caused by various human

activities and large-scale hydraulic works (dams) built along the river, at risk. Extensive agricultural activities and no sustainable management of water resources on both sides of the river (especially around the Delta) pose another threat to the area. The main land uses consist of parks and protected fauna/flora areas, skiing, forestry, grazing, hydro-electricity, urban settlements and scattered industries, fish farming and tourism.

Set out below is the matrix (Table 7) dealing with the various types of degradation identified for the Nestos site and satellite indices that potentially allow such degradation to be identified and monitored.

Table 7. Indices and degradation processes for Nestos

INDICES			DEGRADATION PROCESSES				
Type	Acronym	Description	Landscape modification	Soil salinization	Habitat loss	Increase in invasive species	Trees encroachment
Vegetation Indices	NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	X		X	X	X
	GNDVI	Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	X		X	X	X
	MSAVI ₂	Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	X		X	X	X
	OSAVI	Optimized Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	X		X	X	X
	NDRE	Normalized Difference RedEdge	X		X		
	ARVI	Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index	X		X		X
	EVI ₂	Enhanced Vegetation Index 2	X		X		X
	REP	RedEdge Position	X		X		
	NBR	Normalized Burn Ratio					
	NBR ₂	Normalized Burn Ratio 2					
Water Indices	NDWI ₁	Normalized Difference Water Index 1	X				
	NDWI ₂	Normalized Difference Water Index 2	X				
	MNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index	X				
Soil Indices	NDSI	Normalized Difference Soil Index	X	X	X		
	NDBSI	Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index	X	X	X		
	BI	Bare Index	X	X	X		
Soil Salinity Indices	SSI ₁	Soil Salinity Index-1	X	X			
	SSI ₂	Soil Salinity Index-2	X	X			
	SSI ₃	Soil Salinity Index-3	X	X			
	SI	Salinity Index	X	X			

	SASI	<i>Soil Adjusted Salinity Index</i>	X	X	X		
Drought/Dryness Indices	NDDI	<i>Normalized Difference Drought Index</i>	X	X	X		
	DSI	<i>Desertification Soil Index</i>	X	X	X		

Asterousia

Figure 6. Asterousia

The Asterousia Mountain Range (Figure 6) has been inhabited, grazed, cultivated and supported human communities since ancient times, even though it is deemed to have low productivity on account of its rocky and sloping terrain that is covered by a thin superlayer of soil. The relatively low vegetation cover that is typical of the south-east Mediterranean, coupled

with long dry summers and strong winter rainfalls that are intensified by current climatic deregulation and multidimensional human pressures, have led to an elevated risk of land degradation and desertification.

The Asterousia Mountain Range has seen in recent decades a widespread change in land uses that have been mainly driven by the abandonment of traditional drywall terrace cultivation, the expansion of road networks and infrastructure serving tourism development and RES projects. Another crucial change has been the overgrazing of virtually all of the grasslands due to the steep increase in livestock and the abandonment, which has been driven by the current CAP subsidies policy, of a traditional extensive animal farming model. These human pressures, coupled with the effects of climate deregulation have contributed to an increase in soil loss, erosion and salinization, leading to a degradation of productive arable land, a decline in vegetation cover, loss of biodiversity and the functioning thereof, as well as habitat and landscape modification, all of which will eventually threaten Asterousia with desertification.

Set out below is the matrix (Table 8) dealing with the types of degradation identified for the Asterousia site and the satellite indices that potentially allow such degradation to be identified and monitored.

Table 8. Indices and degradation processes for Asterousia.

INDICES			DEGRADATION PROCESSES											
Type	Acronym	Description	Landsc ape modifica tion	Aridifica tion	Fore st fires	Hydrolog ical modifica tion	Overgra zing	Soil saliniza tion	Soil organi c matte r declin e	Soil erosi on by wate r and wind	Decline in vegetati on commu nity functio ning	Decline in vegetatio n cover/bio mass	Habit at loss	
Vegetation Indices	NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	X		X		X				X	X	X	
	GNDV I	Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	X		X		X				X	X	X	
	MSAVI 2	Modified Soil- Adjusted Vegetation Index	X		X		X				X	X	X	
	OSAVI	Optimized Soil- Adjusted Vegetation Index	X		X		X				X	X	X	
	NDRE	Normalized Difference RedEdge	X		X		X				X	X	X	
	ARVI	Atmospheri cally Resistant Vegetation Index	X				X				X	X	X	
	EVI ₂	Enhanced Vegetation Index 2	X				X				X	X	X	
	REP	RedEdge Position	X				X				X	X	X	
	NBR	Normalized Burn Ratio			X									
	NBR ₂	Normalized Burn Ratio 2			X									
Water Indices	NDWI ₁	Normalized Difference Water Index 1	X			X						X		

	NDWI₂	<i>Normalized Difference Water Index 2</i>	X			X							
	MNDWI	<i>Modified Normalized Difference Water Index</i>	X			X							
Soil Indices	NDSI	<i>Normalized Difference Soil Index</i>	X	X			X	X	X				X
	NDBSI	<i>Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index</i>	X	X			X	X	X				X
	BI	<i>Bare Index</i>	X	X			X	X	X				X
Soil Salinity Indices	SSI₁	<i>Soil Salinity Index-1</i>	X	X				X					
	SSI₂	<i>Soil Salinity Index-2</i>	X	X				X					
	SSI₃	<i>Soil Salinity Index-3</i>	X	X				X					
	SI	<i>Salinity Index</i>	X	X				X					
	SASI	<i>Soil Adjusted Salinity Index</i>	X	X					X				X
Drought/Dryness Indices	NDDI	<i>Normalized Difference Drought Index</i>	X	X			X	X	X				X
	DSI	<i>Desertification Soil Index</i>	X	X			X	X	X				X

6. RS Indices, field data, and statistical analysis methodology

A review of relevant literature has had to be done with a view to identifying the types of statistical analysis to be applied for the purpose of verifying the correlation between field data and remote sensing data. The investigation has consisted of work that:

- has used the main remote sensing indices, with a specific focus on those identified in the A2 action and the types of degradation identified for the pilot sites;
- has monitored restoration work in areas undergoing degradation through remote sensing indices;
- has quantified the ecosystem services before and after the restoration activities;
- has used statistical analysis methodologies with a view to verifying the correlations between satellite indices and other variables.

Being devoted to support the statistical analysis, the search concerned RS indices and degradation phenomena (areas affected by fire, changes in soil cover, vegetation indices, phenology, SOC content, soil salinity indices, desertification indices, etc) selected in the NL4D Project, excluding indicators because the variables to be used to study the correlations between two groups of information must necessarily be quantitative or binary.

A specific insight was gained from the statistical methodologies used in the analysis of the correlations between satellite indices and other variables. The numerous works that were consulted made it possible to organize the relevant information in a matrix (Figure 7) that set out the RS indices used, the analysis of the statistical correlations connected therewith and the other investigated variables and lastly, the statistical methodology and software used.

Indices, Sub-indicators	Statistical Analysis	Correlation types	Software	Data	References
NDVI	Mann-Kendall test Theil-Sen median trend Hurst exponential method	Based on the GIMMS NDVI3g and MODIS normalized difference vegetation index	Modis		https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ExHLQ7enjuWd5yVcigkFq15CAr-EZvX/view?usp=sharing
LCC/Burned areas	Pearson correlation	Correlation between burned areas and PIL Correlation land cover classes	Software IBM SPSS	Modis	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1fW7kw5C48RMNw6jWz8h0nRP_ax3w9r/view?usp=sharing
Burned areas/Climate var	Spearman correlation	Impact of climate variability on wildfire regime		Modis	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1rWF9WaMSFJkw0AYRP039eq8v7ANzM8/view?usp=sharing
Burned areas	General linear model Kolmogorov-Smirnov test Levene test Fisher's (LSD)	For both field measurements and remote sensing estimations, General Li	Landsat-8		https://drive.google.com/file/d/1UhaBpOn2ELTKhuSUrsqTLz5WF2gNv81/view?usp=sharing
LUCC/NDVI/Droughts	Asymmetric Gaussian: This study applied the Asymmetric Gaussians (AG) fitting method, Mann-Kendall test Correlation analysis to the Global Inventory Monitoring and Modeling System (GIMMS)		Landsat-8		https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WwKZfwymxJqzELClZ5ToYJ38XdbMwPF/view?usp=sharing
Soil salinity indices	Multivariate linear regression using multitemporal Landsat images, and the spatiotemporal variations		Landsat		https://drive.google.com/file/d/1wLve5mr9GgV4g0pzy2wPUROK6bWwLm/view?usp=sharing
Soil salinity indices/NDVI/Principal component	Principal component : integrated the salinization index (SI), albedo, normalized difference vegetation index		Sentinel-2		https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AnBGnoYF4Eyzl6CT_xintUCJ0Yad0Q9/view?usp=sharing
	Moran's I LISA	LISA is a local statistical method for spatial variables that reveals the spatial clustering characteristics of observations within spatially adjacent regions			
NDVI	Linear regression Partial and multiple correlation analysis Redundancy analysis and boosted regression trees method	Based on long term NDVI (1982–2015), climate, topographic factors, and	Sentinel-2		https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Ph3g9Sim0hFC2fHo-JeUx7bdUqafB/view?usp=sharing
Burned areas/LCC/PIL	Pearson correlation	Land use and land cover changes to determine if	IBM SPSS statistics	Sentinel-2	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1eQoFuF5fz7KN8a-TZLgPrz3wXY-33tr3/view?usp=sharing
Leaf area index (LAI)	Canonical correlation	Explore phenology and its response to climate change using		Sentinel-2	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1zydDbDIAb3A3MASTN2xkBE99XNka6lp/view?usp=sharing
SOC/LULC	ANOVA test Duncan's new multiple range test (MRT)	Soil quality is related to the total amount of SOC	SAS Enterprise Guide, Version 4.1		https://drive.google.com/file/d/1k71QwTJBJYJKGKJH6i43MQd3b5Yuj/view?usp=sharing
Annual mean fractional vegetation cover	Theil-Sen median trend				https://drive.google.com/file/d/1xkj-vWkIAas1YzxrJUREyOd6puo_UdiZ/view?usp=sharing
NDVI SPEI, human activities	Mann-Kendall test, cc	In this study, the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) and stan	Sentinel-2		https://drive.google.com/file/d/12BCitPzUC8RwECCGmYo-eQDz9v-BXkPv/view?usp=sharing
		We developed a statistical approach to group sub-basins based on similar structure			https://drive.google.com/file/d/1JTPGTiquUsxdWzTH6JSC0gRqQZKAue6S/view?usp=sharing

Figure 7. summarizes the scientific works that have been consulted and that have been organized in a matrix consisting of an index, the aim of the statistical analysis, the type of correlation, the software used, the input data and references.

Results of the search confirm the choice of indices that had previously been selected and it confirmed the need to support the analysis with field data, with a view to making a more accurate assessment of the degradation severity and level. With regard to the restoration work, a critical point arose from the bibliographical analysis, which was that there are often no long-term monitoring projects that allow an assessment of results in face of the initial restoration goals (Río-mena et al., 2020). Satellite remote sensing can be used to monitor the efficiency of medium and long-term interventions. However, additional effort and considerable resources are required for assessing the effective benefits of ecological restoration and quantifying the ecosystem services.

Further challenges are the lack of available and standardized methodologies and the difficulty in obtaining long-term documentation on these projects. In particular, the monitoring systems must trace the activities that need to be conducted and that often require more time to start generating benefits, so as to allow the restoration work outside the timeframe of a project to be monitored (Meroni et al., 2017) (Services and Use, 2016). Ultimately, it has been demonstrated that approaches combining RS-generated information and data, soil-related datasets and field measurements efficiently capture the spatial and temporal variation of ecosystem service provision (Río-mena et al., 2020).

7. Setting of a statistical analysis: definition of data set and methodology

Among the methodologies highlighted by the bibliographical collection, the Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA) has been chosen as a suitable statistical technique for the structure of the dataset available from the pilot sites. The CCA is a Multivariate Statistics technique that allows an analysis to be conducted on the correlations between two datasets. It is used to explore the relationship between two sets of variables, combining them in order to extract the variance of the data matrix through a limited number of independent axes (i.e., “canonical roots”, or “roots”). The first central concept of CCA is the concept of Canonical Variables. The model defines the canonical variables chosen as the two linear combinations of (original) variables coming from opposite data sets, which have the widest possible correlation. After having defined canonical variables, the analysis focuses on the observation of the correlations between the canonical variables and the interpretation of the said relations.

The preparation of the information is a necessary step for applying to all of the pilot sites the available information concerning the ground samples and developing the satellite RS indices, as well as allowing the correlation between the variables involved to be explored.

A preliminary data preparation work had to be conducted, which consisted in re-processing the information (originating from different types of data returned in different formats) so as to make it uniform. The dataset was put in a matrix having an “xls” format that would then be processed.

The Palo Laziale site is the first pilot site for which data concerning ground sample and satellite indices has been collected. The dataset collected for Palo Laziale is structured in:

- a survey of soil parameters consisting in a sample of 20 points, distributed in the Palo Laziale protected area;
- a sample of points set out in the Figure 8 described in scientific research carried out in the framework of the LIFE PRIMED project, during which the field survey collected, in 20 different points, soil samples at different depths (0-10; 10-30; 30-70 cm) that came from four different

types of environments attributable to the three following categories: temporary ponds; floodplain woodland; high Mediterranean scrub; low Mediterranean scrub.

Figure 8. Map of the localization of the soil pits in Palo Laziale
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The point sample was collected between November 2018 and January 2019. Table 9 includes the date of sampling of every single point and the type of zoning in the four types of soil covering what has been previously described.

Table 9. Schedule calendar for soil sampling in Palo Laziale taken from Deliverable Annex A.3 LIFE PRIMED pag. 26

Date	Tipology	N°
29/11/18	Temp Pond	1
29/11/18	Temp pond	2
29/11/18	Wood	3
29/11/18	Temp Pond	4
16/12/18	Temp Pond	5
16/12/18	High scrub	6
16/12/18	Temp pond	7
16/12/18	Wood	8
16/12/18	Low scrub	9
17/01/19	Low scrub	10
17/01/19	Low scrub	11
18/01/19	Low scrub	12
17/01/19	Wood	13
18/01/19	Low scrub	14
17/01/19	Temp pond	15
23/01/19	Low scrub	16
24/01/19	Wood	17
23/01/19	High scrub	18
24/01/19	High scrub	19
23/01/19	Low scrub	20
18/04/19	High scrub	21
18/04/19	High scrub	22
18/04/19	High scrub	23

The average values, ranges, and coefficients of variations for the soil properties of ponds and riparian forests were calculated with regard to all of the soil properties. The coefficients of variations were calculated as the percentages of standard deviations over the mean values (see deliverable Action 3 Life PRIMED). Table 10 and Table 11 show respectively the parameters measured for each soil sample taken in the protected Palo Laziale area and the satellite indices generated from the Sentinel-2 and Pleiades multispectral images.

Table 10. Measured soil parameters

SAND	Sand Average
SILT	Silt Average
CLAY	Clay Average
Tex	Textural
Dep	Depth
pH	pH (H ₂ O) 10g and 25ml
OM	% Organic matter
SAND1	% SAND (2-0,5 mm)
SAND2	% SAND (0,5-0,25)
SAND3	% SAND (0,25-0,053)
SAND4	% SAND (% tot.)
SILT1	% SILT 0,052-0,003
CLAY1	% CLAY <0,003
CEC	CEC (meq/100g)
EC1	Electrical Conductivity (μS/cm) 1:6
EC2	Electrical Conductivity (mS/cm) 1:6
CaCO₃	CaCO ₃ %
SoS	Soluble salts %
Ca	Exchangeable bases (cmol/kg) Ca
Mg	Exchangeable bases (cmol/kg) Mg
Na	Exchangeable bases (cmol/kg) Na
K	Exchangeable bases (cmol/kg) K
ΣB	Σ bases (sum)

Table 11 also sets out the indices obtained from Pleiades images, since the different spatial, spectral and radiometric resolution of the Sentinel2 and Pleiades images does not allow all of the indices for the two datasets that have been identified in Action A2 to be assessed.

Table 11. Palo Laziale indices.

PALO LAZIALE	
SENTINEL-2 (January - July 2020)	PLEIADES (January - July 2020)
VEGETATION INDICES	
NDVI	NDVI
NDMI	Not available
GNDVI	GNDVI
MSAVI2	MSAVI2
OSAVI	OSAVI
NDRE	Not available
ARVI	ARVI
EVI2	EVI2
REP	Not available
PRI	Not available
WATER INDICES	
NDWI1	Not available
NDWI2	NDWI2
MNDWI	Not available
SOIL INDICES	
NDSI	Not available
NDBSI	Not available
BI	Not available
SOIL SALINITY INDICES	
SSI1	SSI1
SSI2	SSI2
SSI3	SSI3
SI	SI

SASI	SASI
DROUGHT/DRYNESS INDICES	
NDDI	Not available
DSI	Not available

The data that has been prepared and mainly processed through the ArcMap GIS software for the spatialization of ground sample data with 2 x2 meters grid cells, which is consistent with the Pleiades images resolution. This has then been carried out also for the indices calculated with Sentinel-2 and data has been extrapolated for both sets. The results are two matrixes of data organized in an “xls” format that are divided according to the input of the image data (Pleiades and Sentinel-2), in which all of the values concerning soil sampling and values coming from the calculated satellite index are indicated for each sample/pixel. The aforementioned operations are essential for the potential processing of data in a correlation analysis model (as is the case with canonical correlations).

8. The form of the monitoring model: Decision Map

In order to highlight how the results of the statistical analysis will be integrated in the final tool to support decisions upon restoration and monitoring, a preliminar definition is here described in the essential structure. The tool is designed for end-users involved in managing and planning protected natural areas and is devoted to guide them in evaluating the available NBS and monitoring options and planning of degraded site monitoring activities, this to reduce the knowledge effort, the subjectivity of the analysis and help to prioritize options. A web based decision making support tool was selected, having a decision making path for the end user side and a decision map behind from the technical side, that matches all elements of the model Fig.9.

The population of the decision map with specific matches come from case studies and general indications from literature. The result is a portfolio of options, ranked on the basis of the environmental relevance and data availability, that the end user can explore trough the web based tool.

Figure 9 - A visual Design of the Tool. The model behind the decision making path can be dynamically adapted to end-user and field expert feedback to match research progress, requests and updates.

Starting from the pressure and threats involved in the degradation processes that have been detected for a site, the user is guided in the selection of the best-fit NBS. Indicators coming both from in-situ data available for the site and remote sensing available indices, will influence the definition of degradation process, restoration solutions and the following monitoring actions need to be taken in order to keep track of the effectiveness.

The user can start either from an identified external pressures (Fig. 10) or from a degradation process which is observable and occurring in the area of interest (Fig. 11).

Which is the external pressure that should be considered tackled or monitored in the restoration process

- Climate Change
- Natural Disasters/extreme events
- Negative land use change
- Unsustainable farming practices
- Unsustainable forestry practices
- Poor land use planning
- Pollution (specify)
- Fauna
- Waste
- Other anthropogenic pressures

Figure 10. A simplified and schematized approach in selecting the external pressure can help the end user in following the right path through their decision-making processes

Pick your Degradation Process

Which Degradation process do you want to tackle, assess or monitor

which degradation process do you want to tackle?

- Aridification
- Change in groundwater level / quality
- Decline in biodiversity
- Decline in biomass
- Decline in vegetation cover
- Forest fires
- Habitat loss
- Decline in vegetation community functioning
- Increase in invasive species
- Increase in weeds
- Landscape modification
- Hydrological modification
- Soil organic matter decline
- Soil salinization
- Soil surface compaction
- Overgrazing
- Soil erosion by water and wind
- Trees encroachment

Go directly to Try another process

← Back Try another process Try another pressure

Figure 11. Example of start of the decision-making process from the Degradation process perspective

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